

THE APPLICATION OF ADVANCED COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY
TO THE AIR FORCE SATELLITE CONTROL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT This paper addresses how planners of the communications architecture for the Air Force Satellite Control Network (AFSCN) are taking advantage of communications technology advancement opportunities for improving network performance and reducing operating costs. Some of the options being studied are targeted to be operational before the end of the decade and intended to support our nation's satellite control capability well into the 21st century. These opportunities include the time-tagging and packetizing of satellite telemetry, commands, secure voice, and ground station status and control information for transmission throughout the Network. These methods could increase the use of commercial and military networks and enhance capabilities. Furthermore, these approaches would complement DISA's (Defense Information Services Agency's) initiatives in satellite communications technology and the Defense Information Systems Network (DISN). However, planners face difficult choices in deciding among numerous emerging technologies. Frame Relay, BISDN (Broadband Integrated Services Digital Network), SMDS (Switched Multi-megabit Data Service), and SONET (Synchronous Optical Network) are among items under consideration for helping to meet future communications capacity needs of the AFSCN. These technologies would also promote interoperability of DoD satellite control and data handling systems by adopting the current tenants of Open Systems Interconnection. Modeling the infusion of these communications technologies in the AFSCN is providing planners with the data to evaluate these options.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Air Force Satellite Control Network (AFSCN) is a network of systems which form part of DoD's satellite command and control capability, performing space vehicle commanding, telemetry processing, orbit determination, network status & scheduling, and other functions. The Network has nine

worldwide remote tracking stations which support the mission vehicles, and two control nodes in the continental U.S. which exchange voice and data with the tracking stations through a variety of communications. Some of the tracking stations are dual sided (these stations have two Telemetry, Tracking, and Commanding (TT&C) antennas at the location) and one is triple sided. Reliable, flexible, and cost effective communications between these resources is a must for the future operating environment of the Network.

The current communications architecture of the AFSCN consists of the establishment of dedicated multiplexed communications between a Satellite Operations Center (also referred to as Mission Control Complex) located within a control node and a Remote Tracking Station. These communications consist of an encrypted primary wideband path using either a military or commercial satellite link, and an encrypted secondary narrowband leased commercial service. Figure 1 is a basic functional block diagram.

FIG 1 - AFSCN COMMUNICATIONS FUNCTIONS

Primary SOC-to-RTS data rates are 192 kbps (single site) and 384 kbps (dual site). Primary RTS-to-SOC data rates are 1.536 Mbps (single) and 3.072 Mbps

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(dual). Secondary (backup) communications are via a combination of terrestrial fiber optics and microwave at rates of 56 kbps and T-1. In order to accommodate communications between approximately a dozen SOCs and the tracking stations, a large investment has been made in systems for switching, multiplexing, patching, encryption, fiber transmission, encoding, modulation, and satellite transmission. While there have been a number of improvements to the communications infrastructure over the years, there have not been changes to its fundamental architecture. It is true that this architecture has served the AFSCN well in meeting its military satellite control mission, but the architecture is becoming increasingly more complex and expensive to operate and maintain.

As a result, the operational user of the AFSCN is initiating an eight year communications upgrade project. The first couple years of this project will involve studies, analyses, and design trades. As part of the Advanced Technology Program for the AFSCN a number of improved methods of passing voice and data between Network resources have been found which are applicable to this project. These methods include evolutionary technology concepts which will facilitate the use of open systems and interoperability. In light of the functions defined above, improvements/alternatives are being sought in the use of packet switch networks, intelligent switching systems, intelligent fault detection/isolation systems, more efficient (less overhead) multiplexing schemes, new coding schemes for compression and error correction, encryption alternatives, ISDN and BISDN, and cellular technology. Discussions of some of these items follow.

II. CURRENT TECHNOLOGY OPTIONS

Present LAN implementations may be a logical first step toward an information transmission environment of the future (Fig 2). The objective of such an architecture would be to take advantage of public (either commercial or DoD) networks. SOCs can take advantage of advances made in LAN architecture for use in passing data between computer resources within these areas.

In support of interoperability, MCC LANs can be internetworked through the use of routers, or tied into a common Fiber Distributed Data Interface backbone. In addition, the MCC LANs can then be networked via Defense Data Network, Air Force Network, Defense Secure Network, or other networks to the resources of the AFSCN. DDN can achieve a probability of

undetected error (using CRC codes) of $4.2 \times 10E-18$ and probability of misdelivered packet of $5.5 \times 10E-12$ [1], which indicates potential to easily satisfy current AFSCN needs of $10E-09$ and $10E-07$ bit error probabilities for commanding and telemetry, respectively.

Likewise, tracking stations would use LAN services for local data communications. Network management would be a coordinated activity between AFSCN personnel and those agencies providing the WAN service, similar to the way long distance telephone carriers work with local telephone companies for phone service.

The primary limitation in present day network systems is the real time delivery of command, control, status, and telemetry data due to capacity limitations of public networks. Telemetry from a tracking station is multiplexed with an Inter-range Instrumentation Group - B (IRIG-B) timing signal to provide the time-tagging of data for processing in the MCC, making real-time delivery necessary. An interim LAN configuration to that in Figure 2 would be to use the public networks for playbacks of recorded data from the tracking station to the control node since real time delivery of this data is not necessary. Even today's X.25 networks with 64 kbps between packet switches can meet some of these needs. This would allow the activity to happen "off line" and not tie up dedicated communications resources which could otherwise be used to support a vehicle contact. These playbacks could also be used for training purposes.

As capabilities for real-time delivery become more mature, a logical next step would be to use the network as a backup to primary communications. The

development of SMDS, SONET, BISDN, and fast-packet switching in general will provide the capabilities needed for public network use in support of primary communications.

III. NEW TECHNOLOGY OPTIONS

Packet switch network technology has been evolving since ARPANET, the first implementation of its kind. A number of commercial and government networks have been developed since that time in response to different needs. The development of fast packet switching systems will allow for a transition of passing satellite control data and voice in real time.

The introduction of frame relay provides options for efficient packet transmission at rates of 1.5 MBPS [2]. However, preliminary tests show that it is still effective at 45 Mbps [3]. This type of technology can be used for the transfer of non-operational text data, such as transfer of resource status messages between control nodes and tracking stations, in real time. Since frame relay provides bandwidth on demand, it is a cost effective method for satisfying burst transmissions of AFSCN resource scheduling information between tracking stations and the nodes. As an example, a 56 kbps Permanent Virtual Circuit, 56 kbps port frame relay round trip from New York/Los Angeles/New York costs \$610-\$2100 monthly, whereas a leased line for the same trip runs about \$4657 [4]. The latter figure is consistent with the \$4514 monthly cost for a 56 kbps link between the node at Falcon AFB, CO, and tracking station at New Boston AFB, NH [5]. Additionally, frame relay could be used for real-time outage reporting and transfer of site status reports back to the control nodes from the remote sites. This information is currently conveyed via FAX, phone, teletype, and low rate electronic messaging. BT TYMNET has proven WAN feasibility by using their Frame Relay Network to connect Seattle, Chicago, New York, Charlotte, Atlanta, Dallas, Los Angeles, and San Francisco for one of their customers [6]. Additionally, AT&T, Compuserve Inc., and U.S. Sprint are planning for international frame relay services with access speeds of 1.024 Mbps and 1.544 Mbps available in 1992. Others are pursuing this as well [7].

The development of cell relay fast packet switching (soon up to 150 Mbps) [Ref 2, p.22] may answer the issues of real time operational data delivery previously mentioned for current packet switch environments (Fig 3). The assembly of data into a greater number of smaller, fixed length packets will help

reduce network delays. Additionally, current separate and costly "primary" and "secondary" communications can be eliminated in favor of priority management schemes employed in the public network, thereby increasing robustness and reducing risk of data loss during "failovers" from primary to secondary communications. Switched Multi-megabit Data Service (SMDS) will provide the framework for supporting this type of environment by furnishing a wide area public networks at rates (initially) of 1.5 Mbps and 45 Mbps [Ref 2, p.22].

The use of cell relay will also allow for integration of voice transmission with data over networks. Cell relay is more effective than frame relay for voice transmission due to the decrease in networks delays [8]. This would allow for the integration of the AFSCN voice traffic with the data, a concept consistent with those of Broadband Integrated Services Digital Network (BISDN).

FIG 3 - AFSCN COMM IN ATM/SONET ENVIRONMENT

Presently it is difficult to discuss the use of fast-packet, particularly cell relay, networks without including the need for a high speed medium and transport method to pass the packets. Standards for optical transmission developed under SONET can provide the basis for communication at these rates [Ref 2, p.22]. Additionally, the ability to transmit data over great distances is becoming much more efficient through new advances in fiber technology, such as fiber doping. These advances will help provide the necessary long haul communications capabilities between remote tracking stations and control nodes in addition to providing the low-noise medium required by fast packet technologies. An initial step would be to use these systems between

CONUS tracking stations and the control nodes.

IV. INITIAL INVESTIGATION

The Defense Information Services Agency (DISA), formerly Defense Communications Agency, is actively pursuing integration of DoD network services. Defense Integrated Services Network (DISN) Near Term will integrate non-secure voice, video, and services provided by DDN, AFnet, Navnet, DLAnet, and others. DISN Far Term will integrate DISN Near Term with messaging, secure voice, and FTS 2000 services. As the integration of these systems progresses it will become more feasible to use these resources for AFSCN communications.

In the meantime, the management of the AFSCN Advanced Technology Program is planning a demonstration to evaluate the feasibility of using current packet switch networks (such as DDN) for passing AFSCN data. This demonstration will focus on determining effects on the integrity of telemetry data received from a tracking station. These activities will include modelling the performance of using these systems under a variety of scenarios. There will also be analyses of the use of fast-packet systems for AFSCN communications. The initial activities of the demonstration will require an accurate determination of traffic flow between the tracking stations and control nodes. A high level description of the types of data passed between nodes and tracking stations follows.

A. Node to Station Data

Data transmitted from the node to the station includes two types of messages [9]: (1) Configuration/Control and (2) Satellite Vehicle commands. Both of these message types are bursty in nature, thereby making cell switching desirable for efficient use of bandwidth. Commands are formed into ADCCP protocol packets of up to 4096 bytes, including a 2 byte header. The header includes a packet sequence identification.

These messages are multiplexed with voice and other data to an aggregate of 192 kbps (single station) or 384 kbps (dual). The aggregate is then encrypted prior to transmission to SATCOM (ref Fig 1). These encryption devices do not support operation in a packet switch environment, so a different encryption mechanism would be necessary, possibly at the upper layers of the OSI model. It is also necessary to derive the statistics of the data streams in order to determine the distribution and arrival rate of packets into the network in order to determine performance characteristics. Additionally

some method of priority queuing must be employed since some messages have higher priority than others.

B. Station to Node Data

Data transmitted from the station to the node also includes two types of messages [Ibid]: (1) Station status and (2) S/V command echoes. Station status includes time-tagged telemetry data received from the s/v, antenna tracking data. Command echoes are formed into packets (maximum length 257 bytes) prior to transmission.

As with the node-to-station traffic, these data messages are multiplexed and encrypted prior to transmission. Aggregate data rates are 1.536 Mbps (single) and 3.072 Mbps (dual). This data will be less bursty. Again, analysis must be performed to determine the statistics of the data leaving the station. Priority queuing is needed for this traffic as well.

V. CONCLUSION

Progress in the areas of network telecommunications indicates potential for using public networks as an effective means of passing AFSCN data. Additional investigation is required to determine cost savings, risk, performance, and security issues of using commercial public networks for AFSCN communications. In particular, evaluation of Quality of Service metrics is required to determine end-to-end bit error rate and delay improvements for going to fast packet networks for AFSCN communications. Along with this, cost analyses are required to determine cost vs benefit ratios for using these systems. It also is not clear how data security will be implemented in these environments. Ideally, this would be done at the upper layers of the OSI model. Demonstrations and analyses will provide some initial answers to some of these issues, but continued research is needed.

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